

Leucaena as green leaf manure for lowland rice

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Leucaena leucocephala is a renewable source of green manure. On dry basis, the tender loppings contain 4.3% N. We tested the contribution of 10 t leucaena/ha to growth and yield of IR20 using 4 levels of N (0, 50, 75, and 100 kg/ha) during rabi 1986-87, in 3 replications. Soil was clay loam with 0.06% total N, low Olsen's P (8.6 kg/ha), 70 ppm exchangeable K, pH 7.4, CEC 18.6 meq/100 g, and 0.34% organic C.

Fresh tender loppings of 50-d-old leucaena (Hawaiian Giant Var. K8) harvested from 2-yr-old plants were

Effect of leucaena as green leaf manure on growth characters, yield components, and grain yield of rice (IR20). Madurai, India, 1986-87 rabi.

Treatment	Growth character		Yield component				Grain yield (t/ha)
	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no./hill)	Productive tillers (no./hill)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	1000-grain (g)	
No N	72.2	5.8	4.2	18.62	78.0	16.42	2.8
Leucaena at 10 t/ha	82.6	8.0	5.8	19.76	93.2	18.60	3.6
50 kg N/ha alone	83.0	7.8	6.0	19.86	92.6	18.64	3.6
50 kg N/ha + leucaena	92.4	8.8	8.0	20.64	105.6	19.56	4.3
75 kg N/ha alone	91.4	8.6	7.2	20.52	99.8	18.78	4.0
75 kg N/ha + leucaena	97.4	10.2	9.8	21.32	110.2	20.74	4.8
100 kg N/ha alone	93.8	9.2	8.2	20.96	104.6	19.68	4.3
LSD (0.05)	3.1	0.7	1.1	0.46	3.9	0.78	0.4

incorporated 10 d before planting rice. A basal dose of 22 kg P, 41.5 kg K, and 50% of N was applied just before planting; the rest of N was topdressed in 2 equal splits 30 and 40 d after transplanting.

Leucaena as leaf manure combined

with fertilizer N at suboptimal levels increased growth and yield over suboptimal N alone (see table). Leucaena with 75 kg N/ha gave highest grain yield (4.8 t/ha), better than that with 100 kg N/ha (4.3 t/ha). Applying 50 kg N with leucaena gave 4.3 t/ha. □

Fertilizer requirement of rice - rice - green manure cropping system

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We assessed the fertilizer requirements of rice - rice - green manure, a major

cropping system in Central Kerala, at RARS, Pattambi, 1983 to 1986.

Green manure *Sesbania speciosa* was raised (Feb-May) and incorporated before the kharif crop (Jan-Sep), at 4.3 t/ha (21.1% dry matter, 2.4% N, 0.31% P, and 1.42% K). The rabi crop (Sep-Jan) was given no organic manure. The kharif and rabi rices (Jaya variety) were given 50, 75, and 100% of the fertilizer dose 90-45-45 kg NPK/ha. The sandy loam soil contained 1.38% organic C, 0.025% available N, 19.1 kg

available P, and 222.3 kg available K/ha. The pH was 5.4 and cation exchange capacity 12.6 meq/100 g soil.

The treatment receiving 75% of the fertilizer dose in each season yielded the same as that receiving 100% (see table). □

Effect of fertilizer treatments on grain and straw yields of rice - rice - green manure cropping system. Pattambi, Kerala, India, 1983-86.

Treatment	Percentage of fertilizer dose		Mean grain yield (t/ha)			Mean straw yield (t/ha)		
	Kharif	Rabi	Kharif	Rabi	Total for the system	Kharif	Rabi	Total for the system
T ₁	100	100	3.3	3.8	7.1	2.9	3.2	6.1
T ₂	100	75	3.1	3.6	6.7	3.0	3.0	6.0
T ₃	100	50	2.8	3.6	6.4	3.1	3.0	6.1
T ₄	75	100	2.9	4.1	7.0	3.0	3.4	6.4
T ₅	75	75	3.2	3.7	6.9	3.0	3.1	6.1
T ₆	75	50	3.2	3.1	6.3	2.5	2.3	4.8
T ₇	50	100	3.0	3.7	6.7	2.6	3.0	5.6
T ₈	50	75	3.1	3.4	6.5	2.5	2.5	5.0
T ₉	50	50	2.9	3.4	6.3	2.8	2.7	5.5
LSD (0.05)					0.4			0.6

Effect of rice plants on fertilizer N losses in flooded soil

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We evaluated the influence of rice plants on fertilizer N losses from flooded soil in greenhouse experiments in 1986-87 with planted (variety M201) and unplanted treatments. Five kg of Myers clay soil (pH 6.6, 0.1% total N) in 1986, and 3 kg of Sacramento clay soil (pH 7.7, 0.1% total N) in 1987 were weighed into plastic pots after air-drying and screening.

Solutions of ¹⁵N-labeled KNO₃ and urea were separately mixed with soil

Table 1. Mass balance of 300 mg incorporated KNO₃-N and urea N in flooded soil at grain maturity stage, 1986.

¹⁵ N fraction	¹⁵ N recovery (%)		Difference between treatments ^a (mg/pot)
	Planted	Un-planted	
KNO ₃			
Soil	3.5	3.7	
Plant	1.2	—	
Recovered	4.6	3.7	
Unaccounted for	95.4	96.3	2.8 ^{ns}
Urea			
Soil	43.9	78.1	
Plant	43.6	—	
Recovered	87.5	78.1	
Unaccounted for	12.5	21.9	28.3*

^a* = significant at 5%, ns = not significant by T-test.

Table 2. Mass balance of 600 mg banded urea N in flooded soil at 3 growth stages, 1987.

¹⁵ N fraction	¹⁵ N recovery (%)		Difference between treatments ^a (mg/pot)
	Planted	Un-planted	
<i>Six-leaf stage</i>			
Soil	81.6	91.5	
Plant	13.7	—	
Recovered	95.3	91.5	
Unaccounted for	4.7	8.5	23.0 ^{ns}
<i>Panicle initiation stage</i>			
Soil	56.6	74.6	
Plant	24.6	—	
Recovered	81.2	74.6	
Unaccounted for	18.8	25.4	39.5 ^{ns}
<i>Grain maturity stage</i>			
Soil	57.9	59.0	
Plant	23.4	—	
Recovered	81.3	59.0	
Unaccounted for	18.7	41.0	134.0**

^a** = significant at 1%, ns = not significant by T-test.

samples at 300 mg N/pot in 1986. In 1987, only ¹⁵N-labeled urea solution was used at 600 mg N/pot. Band application was simulated by applying solution at a depth of 5 cm in a circle 8 cm in diameter.

Rice plants had no significant effect on losses of KNO₃-N (Table 1). Loss was more than 95% in both planted and unplanted pots, probably through denitrification. With urea (Table 1, 2), N losses were significantly higher from unplanted pots in both years.

The difference between unplanted and planted treatments in urea N unaccounted for was greater in the banded application in 1987 (22.3%) than in incorporated urea in 1986 (9.4%). Since twice as much urea was band applied, we cannot conclude whether its losses were higher than those with

incorporation.

Growing rice plants effectively reduced the urea N losses from flooded soil, even though plant roots sometimes stimulated denitrification. Urea N losses were probably due to ammonia volatilization, but denitrification cannot be ruled out. □

Organic and inorganic N effect on rice

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We studied the integrated effects of dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata*, azolla *Azolla pinnata*, and N, P, and K fertilizers during winter 1987 at TRRI, in medium-duration IR20. The soil was clayey loam with available status of 222 kg N, 29.9 kg P, and 12.45 kg K/ha. pH was 7.3.

One week before transplanting rice, 60-d-old dhaincha (3.2% N, 0.31% P,

and 1.1% K on dry weight basis) was cut and incorporated at 12.5 t/ha. One week after transplanting, azolla at 1 t/ha on fresh weight basis (3.07% N, 0.07% P, and 0.15% K on dry weight basis) was applied and allowed to multiply and disintegrate by itself.

Azolla improved grain yield when applied with inorganic N or with dhaincha (see table).

Dhaincha at 12.5 t/ha gave significantly better grain yield than 40 kg N. Dhaincha applied with 40 kg N was even better than 80 kg N.

The combined application of dhaincha and azolla was equal to 80 kg N/ha. □

Effects of dhaincha and azolla on grain yield of IR20. Aduthurai, India, 1987 winter.

Treatment	Mean plant height (cm)	Productive tillers (no.)	Grain yield (t/ha)
1. Control	73.3	6.8	2.7
2. 0 kg N + 8.7 kg P + 16.6 kg K/ha	74.4	7.0	2.9
3. 40 kg N + 8.7 kg P + 16.6 kg K/ha	73.7	7.6	3.2
4. Azolla + treatment 2	71.2	6.2	2.9
5. Azolla + treatment 3	75.6	7.5	3.7
6. Dhaincha + treatment 2	82.7	8.5	4.0
7. Dhaincha + treatment 3	84.5	9.9	4.6
8. Dhaincha + azolla + treatment 2	81.9	9.0	4.4
9. 80 kg N + 17.4 kg P + 33.2 kg K/ha	77.1	8.4	4.1
LSD (P = 0.05)	5.3	0.9	0.4

Effect of plant spacing on N release of sulfur-coated urea (SCU) in wetland rice

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SCU's controlled release rate helps reduce N losses in wetland soil, thereby producing higher yields than other urea materials. As the sulfur coating

decomposes, N is released. This process is affected by temperature, soil microbial activity, soil water, method of application, and coating characteristics.

To examine an additional factor, we studied the effect of plant spacing on N release patterns of SCU in wetland rice.

We used 2 spacings, 15 × 20 cm and 20 × 10 cm, in a sandy loam soil (Typic Ustochrept). The soil had pH 8.5, EC 0.15 dS/m, 0.23% organic C, 0.04% total N, and 4 meq cation exchange